

TEACHING METHODS TO INCREASE LEARNING ENGLISH OF YOUNG CHILDREN.

Normo'minova Mohigul Abdirasul qizi

3rd year student of Termiz State University,
Foreign language and literature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7197770>

Annotation: Today, like all fields, the demand and need for learning a foreign language has increased significantly. The high demand for children to learn a foreign language, especially in the era of modern innovations, is a clear example of our word. Various modern and innovative methods are being created by scientists and psychologists. In this regard, special textbooks and manuals have been developed for young children and primary school students. In particular, English for children, Kids English, Funny English songs for children are examples of these.

Keywords: foreign language, grammatical rules, English alphabet

Our country has been paying attention to a lot of areas in the last 10 years. Including the Presidential Decree "On further improvement of the system of foreign language learning" adopted on December 10, 2012, as well as the study of foreign languages in the primary classes of general education schools starting from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of teaching is a clear example of it. Today, not only school, secondary and higher education students, but also MTM trainees, as well as employees working in various fields, learn a foreign language, especially English. The main reason for this is economic science and cultural learning the languages of developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development. Language learning is definitely divided into young periods, for example, according to statistical data, children learn a foreign language faster and easier than adults. The fact that the passion is stronger than that of adults is that children have more time is a clear example. It should not be forgotten that 5-8-year-old children do not understand the essence of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is certainly not without benefits to start teaching language to elementary school students with grammatical rules. Otherwise, children will not learn the language. Therefore, teaching young children a foreign language is a very difficult and responsible task. To make teaching a foreign language meaningful and effective to young children, the following methods can be used.

- First of all, it is an effective way for children to learn the English alphabet in the form of songs rather than just memorizing it. In addition, games based on

physical and mental movements, songs, movies and cartoons, as well as picture dictionaries are examples of this. In young children, we can observe that it is easier for them to learn by seeing, hearing and repeating. In this respect, they differ from adults. It is worth noting one more thing that the teacher can create an atmosphere in the classroom, the students' interest in the subject and their worldview will increase. For example, if the topic is about wild animals, even if the teacher pastes pictures of animals on the board or brings his figurines, the children will have an idea about it. and their vocabulary increases.

-Practical training (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers).

This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "A pedagogue who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory should use the child's sensory organs as much as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscles, and even if possible should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering".

For example: when a student tastes an apple, the teacher should inform about its color, whether it is red or green, taste sweet or sour, smell, and give other children information about that fruit. If the teacher asks the students the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers the time when he ate the fruit. This method ensures that the student will retain the information in his memory for a long time.

- Through visual aids, posters, books.

- It is not without benefit to teach by tying things to things that are visible and often used in everyday life.

We know that children are curious and they quickly get bored of the same things. For this reason, it requires great skill and creativity from the teacher to interest and attract the child.

In conclusion, language teaching to young children should not be done as an obligation, but as an interesting activity, using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi. He also knew many foreign languages perfectly, was able to speak and create in these languages with ease. knows".

Bibliographic description:

1. Yuldasheva, D. A. Innovative methods of teaching English to young children / D. A. Yuldasheva. - Text: neposredstvennyy // Molodoy uchenyy. 2017. - No. 4.2 (138.2). - S. 60-61. - URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39159/> (data processing: 07.10.2022) -

